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RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND THE SEMANTICS OF UNIVERSITY'S THIRD MISSION. A THEORETICAL DISCUSSION¹

I - RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH

Science is a very limited social phenomenon in the history of mankind: it is a form of knowledge production restricted to a relatively small number of societies. Human activities characterized by substantial resemblances with those that are nowadays defined as scientific date back to no longer than some four hundred years ago, when – between the sixteenth and the seventeenth century, in the «western world» – science progressively emancipated from theology and speculation. From then on, scientific activities evolved from initial amateurship and the institutionalization and autonomization of a «new science» begun (Mendelsohn 1977; Elias 1982) till it eventually developed into the most recent forms of Big Science.

That complex process – which is far from being a linear one – has undergone a major acceleration in the second half of the nineteenth century, notably after World War II. The extension and rapidity of changes concern both the «internal» as well as the «external» history of science. Indeed, the very distinction between what is to be considered as inherently internal and what is external to science has become fuzzy. For instance, the relationships between such phenomena as the epistemic displacement of scientific knowledge pointed out by the Kuhnian and post-Kuhnian analysis, the gradual consolidation of new modes of scientific knowledge production (Gibbons et al. 1994), the emergence of inedited forms of science-society interactions and of changing public understandings of science grew more and more complex and imbricated. The very social meaning of science, its place and function in society, the role and status of researchers and of scientific knowledge production are nowadays more than in the past significantly questioned as the need arises for science to be «socially robust» (Novotny et al. 2001). Governance of scientific institutions and organizations, of their modes of production and reproduction,

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as well as of funding of research activities, are deeply connected to such a questioning, which implies the redefinition of the borders of the scientific field and, at the same time, has profound backlashes on the dynamics which are internal to that field itself (Bourdieu 1997, 2001). In fact, what happens on those very borders – where the sphere of human activities that can be defined as «scientific» meet with other spheres of societal life and society at large – is crucial not only to the sociology of science, but to anyone who aims at critically define and/or carry out responsible research.

The speed of change that science and technology presently face, the very direction of such a change, as well as the overall ethical implications and societal impacts of scientific research are the major concerns that led the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission to adopt *ad hoc* strategies aimed at bringing scientific research closer to citizens and societal needs².

Significantly enough, the «Science and Society» Action Plan launched by the European Commission (EC) in 2001 to set out a new strategy to make science more accessible to European citizens, was renamed «Science *in* Society», in 2007, under the 7th Framework Programme³. More recently, the Action Plan was newly labelled «Science *with and for* Society» in order to clearly express the Commission's political commitment that underlies the new Framework for Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI):

The grand societal challenges that lie before us will have a far better chance of being tackled if all societal actors are fully engaged in the co-construction of innovative solutions, products and services. Responsible Research and Innovation means that societal actors work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes, with the values, needs and expectations of European society. RRI is an ambitious challenge for the creation of a Research and Innovation policy driven by the needs of society and engaging all societal actors via inclusive participatory approaches (EC 2012: 1).

Such an ambitious engagement deserves a close look, not only as to the key issues upon which, according to the EC, RRI is based, but also as to some relevant underlying assumptions on which it is based⁴. In the following pages we will discuss some theoretical aspects of responsibility and we will try to propose a conceptual framework to better understand some aspects of science-society relationships by examining the semantics of the so called «third mission» of universities⁵.

² According to Eurobarometer 401 on Responsible Research and Innovation (2013), European citizens are concerned about the speed of change of science and technology and their potential impacts, as 74% among them agree that the developments of science and technology could have unforeseen negative side-effects on health and the environment; and 62% agree that science makes our way of life change too fast. Moreover, 76% of respondents to Eurobarometer agree that the EU should take measures to address the ethical risk of new technologies.

³ For an overview, see Anichini - de Cheveigné (2012). On the emergence of RRI within EU policy structures, see de Saille (2015).

⁴ The RRI framework consists of six keys: engagement of all societal actors, gender equality, science education, ethics, open access to results of publicly funded research and governance.

⁵ According to Eurostat and Ocse, most of the publicly funded and of fundamental research presently run in Italy as well as in the rest of European countries is run by universities.

Before the Pope's election, each Cardinal taking part in the Conclave is called to make an oath: «*Et ego, N., Cardinalis N., spondeo, voveo, ac iuro sic me Deus adiuvet et haec Sancta Dei Evangelia, quae manu mea tengo*».

Literally, each Cardinal «promise(s), vow(s) and swear(s)». In fact, *spondēre* (to promise) is the Latin verb which – composed with the prefix *re* which indicates the repetition of an action in the opposite direction – originates the modern word «responsibility». According to the dictionary, that term can be used to designate the state or fact of *having a duty* to deal with something or of *having control* over someone; the state or fact of *being accountable* or to blame for something; the *opportunity or ability to act independently* and take decisions without authorization. Such meanings can be found in the Italian term *responsabilità*, in the Spanish *responsabilidad*, the French *responsabilité*, or the Portuguese *responsabilidade* which all visibly share the same etymology.

Strangely enough, unlike those languages that have much clearer Latin origins, the English vocabulary counts another word that originates from *respondēre*. «Responsiveness» is the noun used to indicate the quality or state of reacting or replying quickly or favourably, as to a suggestion, initiative etc. Biologists generally use that word to indicate the ability of living things to respond to stimuli coming from the external environment. Similarly, when applied to machinery, the term is used to designate the capacity of a machine or system to adjust quickly to suddenly altered external conditions.

Clearly enough, time is a key factor when it comes to responsiveness: rapidity, i.e. the lapse of time occurring between stimulus and response, is crucial. The role of time is not as clear when it comes to tracing back the origins of a given fact or phenomenon and it gets even more ambiguous when responsibilities are sought. We know for instance that in 1905 Albert Einstein enunciated the principle of mass-energy equivalence expressed by the well known equation $E = mc^2$. We also know that the theoretical foundation of the atomic bomb lies on such a principle. Therefore, one can say that that principle is at the origins of the A bomb. Which does not necessarily imply the possibility of holding Einstein responsible for the death of the about 129,000 people who died in august 1945 in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. Rather, some tend to trace Einstein's implication with the development of the technology that brought to the achievement of the A bomb in the letter he signed in 1939 which exhorted the U.S. President F.D. Roosevelt to promote a program to investigate the possibility of building a nuclear device using the latest discoveries in nuclear physics. As it is well known, in that same year, the Manhattan Project was launched and eventually grew much larger when its initial objectives were significantly modified in 1942 and came to involve some 130,000 people who worked under Robert Oppenheimer's scientific direction. Einstein was definitely unrelated to such developments and did not have any mean to exert an influence whatsoever on the ongoing process.

The intricate history of the making of the A bomb is a classic for the understanding of science's and scientists' responsibilities, which cannot here be adequately recalled and analyzed as to all its relevant implications. What is relevant to retain here by means of a simple comparison between Einstein's and Oppenheimer's positions is that *express*

involvement in the process is one of the key components we tend to associate with the attribution of a strong or weak degree of responsibility. Such a factor has very much to do with such things as *the actual possibility of making a change*, i.e. control and power. Also, it has very much to do with the *expectations* that one can attach to an action, a set of actions, or, eventually, inactions. Thus, high degrees of responsibility are normally attached to intention, power, information. *Spondēre* is an intentional act of making a *promise*, assuming an *obligation*, undertaking an *engagement* which binds together the poles of a relationship that is held together by a set of reciprocal expectations based on the possibility/capacity to *anticipate* the consequences of their acts.

Since people are expected to be able to anticipate the fallouts of what they do – or don't do – they can be called upon to respond for such action(s) – or inaction(s) – i.e. to give answers about their conducts. That dimension of responsibility is called «answerability».

One can also be called upon to respond for acts that were not his or hers. Most normative systems provide for such a dimension of responsibility, that is known as «imputability» (Schlenker et al. 1994). Such is for instance the case when parents must respond for the consequences of their children's behaviour, or when a social group claims by another group for reparation to the arm provoked by just one of that second group's members, as it is often the case in certain traditional societies. It is noteworthy that those possible declinations of imputability lead us to reappraise and restrict the role of anticipation as a distinctive component of responsibility. In fact, those examples clearly show that the connection between responsibility/imputability and rational action is not a necessary one.

As it is well known, such a connection is nonetheless at the core of the classic weberian couple *Verantwortungsethik* vs. *Gesinnungsethik* (ethics of responsibility vs. ethics of ultimate ends) as both terms of the dichotomy are conceived building on guiding principles of rational action (Weber 1921). That distinction largely fits in the wider philosophical debate on ethics which confronts consequentialist moral positions with deontologist ones. From a sociological point of view, that distinction is anchored to the existing relationship between expectations and anticipation which can be traced back in Parson's notion of «double contingency» implied in social interactions (Parsons and Shils 1951). That very notion is crucial to understand the relational nature of responsibility which is shaped within a circular system of expectations and counter-expectations that make anticipation possible (Arnaldi - Bianchi in press). Humans orient their actions on the basis of such a complex system of interactions: they cannot be regarded as individuals who decide and act just by referring to an abstract set of norms, but rather in the framework of a complex relational system in which they act and which is made of other persons, as well as animated and unanimated objects (Dodier 1995). That system is not necessarily totally intelligible to actors, nor is it static: a relational world which is understood and manipulated by social actors as they get along in the process of interaction by means of varying adaptation strategies, judgement perspectives and justification options (Boltanski - Thévenot 1991).

Information and communication technologies nowadays widen the set of possible interactions among significant others, thus considerably expanding the spheres of dou-

ble contingencies, and therefore exponentially amplifying the horizon of anticipation to a potentially infinite number of interactions and possible unattended/unintended consequences of decisions and actions. Obviously enough, that does not imply the end of responsibility – although various forms of complexity are often recalled by societal actors to advocate extraneity to fallouts of their actions or behaviors. But that surely indicates that the role of the rational component of action as conceived by Weber must be reconsidered and that the sphere of imputation gains importance, thus redefining and potentially reducing the ambits of liability, i.e. the possibility to make one accountable and respond for his or her behavior (Vincent 2011).

In contemporary societies, such a potentially wider room for actors' freedom from social obligations is counterbalanced by the parallel amplification of potential consequences of behaviors which is connected to wider access than in the past to technologies and technological devices that expand and potentiate human actions. Hence, the need to define the ambits of «responsible freedom» (Cesareo - Vaccarini 2006).

III - RRI AND THIRD MISSION

When applied to scientific research, those premises lead to fundamental requirements for it to be defined «responsible».

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) refers to the comprehensive approach of proceeding in research and innovation in ways that allow all stakeholders that are involved in the processes of research and innovation at an early stage (A) to obtain relevant knowledge on the consequences of the outcomes of their actions and on the range of options open to them and (B) to effectively evaluate both outcomes and options in terms of societal needs and moral values and (C) to use these considerations (under A and B) as functional requirements for design and development of new research, products and services (EC 2013: 3).

According to such ambitious objectives both R&I processes and outcomes need to respond to a definite set of requirements, Kupper et al. say (2015). Notably, four clusters of process requirements are needed to ensure RRI (*ivi*: 9-10):

a. diversity and inclusion, calling «for the involvement of a wide range of stakeholders in the early development of science and technology»;

b. openness and transparency, as «conditions for accountability, liability and thus responsibility»;

c. anticipation and reflexivity, to ensure the understanding of «how the present dynamics of research and innovation practice [may] shape the future», as well as «learning about both the definitions of the problem(s) issue, commitments, practices, and individual and institutional values, assumptions and routines»;

d. responsiveness and adaptive change, to ensure researchers promptly respond «to emerging knowledge, perspectives, views and norms» and provide for «a capacity to change or shape existing routines».

Clearly enough, such process requirements, which were identified on the basis of systematic review of literature on responsible research and innovation, incorporate the

major issues pointed out in the previous pages. According to authors, they can eventually lead to responsible outcomes as to learning (engaged publics, responsible actors, responsible institutions) and research and innovation (ethically acceptable, sustainable, socially desirable), that may significantly impact on the solution of societal challenges (p. 10).

Process requirements and outcomes of responsible research and innovation may be operationalised to identify quality criteria and practice standards for research that can significantly move the debate on evaluation of research impact well beyond the asphyxial dimension of the so called «impact factor» (Weinberg 1963; Wickson - Carew 2014). It is in fact widely known that impact factor is far from assessing the actual impact of a scientific product, but rather its popularity within the scientific community (Bertaux 2008) and is thus based on an inaccurate conception of impact and very limited ideas about the fallouts of scientific activities which do not seem to acknowledge the profound changes that have affected science-society relationships. In that respect, the layman's views testified by recent Eurobarometers on attitudes towards science (see footnote 2 above) seem to take the relevance of impacts of the advancements of science and technology on people's everyday life much more seriously than the most diffused «measures» of impact based on mere citation analysis.

IV - SEMANTICS OF THIRD MISSION: THE REPAIRED SCHEME

Universities tend to comprehend issues that concern relationships between their activities and society within the wider notion of their third mission, which is therefore generically used to refer to their direct and indirect contribution to society. Notwithstanding the large variety of practices that fall within them, consensus is generally widespread about universities' core missions of teaching and research. Agreement is definitely less generalized about the notion of third mission, which is used to designate a very large set of strategies and practices which engage universities beyond the campus gates (Gleeson 2010). Semantics of that expressions may thus differ significantly as to the kind of university-society relations (varying from outreach, to consultation, collaboration or shared leadership), as well as to their geographical extension (at local, regional, national or international level).

Since, as said above, responsibility is based on a complex dynamics of expectations which may lead to certain configurations of anticipation – i.e. being responsibility inherently relational – clearly defining the different kind of relationships that may take form between universities and society – i.e. better understanding the semantics of third mission – becomes crucial when it comes to Responsible Research and Innovation.

In the following pages such an issue will be dealt with by discussing some relevant components of the concept of third mission which concern key relational aspects (regulatory principles and involvement/participation of stakeholders), as well as drivers for action (interests) that are connected to different epistemologies and kind of impacts. Three possible declinations will be identified for each one of those components which taken altogether will compose three relevant and relatively autonomous semantic areas of the concept of third mission which correspond respectively to knowledge transfer, public engagement and community engagement. On the basis of such dis-

cussion, the RePAIED chart (Regulatory principles, Participation, Actors' Interest and Emancipatory Dynamics) will be proposed to schematically summarize the main characteristics of those three different dimensions of the semantics of third mission. Such RePAIED scheme builds upon the author's previous elaborations (see, for instance, Vargiu 2014) and conference presentations.

As changes affect Higher Education Systems and Institutions worldwide, also «regulatory changes occur in various national contexts, as well as a significant increase in transnational regulations and attempts to standardize and control education and research across national boundaries» (Wedlin 2008: 145). That is significantly connected, author states, with a growing «marketization» of higher education institutions. Such a marketization process can be regarded as a fallout of a specific form of regulation, whereas the concept itself of regulation is declined from a strictly sociological perspective, i.e. is intended as *social regulation*.

The very notion of social regulation is used to refer to the set of criteria and modes by means of which resources are allocated within a given social group, and it thus deals with the way such a social groups functions, how it prevents and solves conflicts, and the like. In other words: how social order is made possible and kept (Streeck - Schmitter 1985). It can be therefore stated that the very heart of the key issue of sociological enquiry is rooted in the notion of social regulation. In that sense, Durkheim's study of anomy, rather than Parson's questioning about institutionalization, value-norms systems and social control, or Pareto's ideas about social equilibrium all feed upon the issue of social regulation (Fantozzi 2008: 54-58; Merler 1996). Nonetheless, those authors only indirectly contribute to a theory of social regulation, whereas such works as Karl Polanyi's (1944) are more specifically dedicated to the theoretical articulation of such a concept. That author's classical tripartition which identifies the state, the market and the community as main regulatory spaces is useful to our purposes here.

In fact, the progressive diffusion of the idea that universities should be managed as business enterprises and become «entrepreneurial» universities (Clark 1998) is generally coupled by the progressive move from principally state driven higher education system governance to a market driven one (Oecd 2008; Neave - van Vught 1994; Clark 1983). Accordingly, reference can be made to the respective prevailing regulatory principles which refer to redistribution (state) and exchange (market). Such statements as those contained in the UK's Government Paper on Science and Innovation (2000: 27) which assign a pivotal role to universities in acting as «major agents of economic growth», clearly express such a market centred conception of university-society relationships. On the other hand, other narratives and approaches are rather connected to an idea of third mission as based on reciprocity and symmetry of relationships. Which, again according to Polanyi's view, are typical of community.

Community engagement describes the collaboration between institutions of higher education and their larger community (local, regional/state, national, global) for the mutually beneficial exchange of knowledge and resources in a context of partnership and reciprocity (Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Learning 2007: 1).

Exchange, redistribution and reciprocity can therefore be seen as distinctive components – although not totally exclusive – of three different dimensions of the third mission of universities. We can further build on that tripartition by associating the three distinct kinds of relationship identified by Polanyi – respectively asymmetric, centric and symmetric – with three idealtypes of participation that, according to Ceri (1998), can be resumed as follows: a) *participation as influence*, which implies low degrees of aggregation and equalization among individuals or groups (thus asymmetry of relations typical of market driven regulation); b) *participation as cooperation*, which is based on low levels of aggregation combined with high degrees of equalization (centric kinds of relationships typical of state driven regulation); c) *participation as involvement and action*, which implies high levels of aggregation and equalization (symmetric relationships based on reciprocity and solidarity: community driven regulation).

As Saxena points out (1998: 112), people are likely to participate and take action when they see an interest in it: be that a particularistic or a universalistic one. This leads us to connect the double tripartition briefly sketched above building on certain declinations of regulation and participation to Habermas' knowledge theory (1968) which highlights the relationships between stakeholders, their different interests in knowledge production and the outcomes of research activities. In short, Habermas' idea is that if prevailing interests are mainly instrumental and technical, the kind of connected epistemology shall be empirical-analytical and the prevailing kind of action will be a strategic one. Similarly, mainly practical interests will lead to a hermeneutic-interpretative epistemology through mechanical action. Finally, emancipative interests are connected to a critical approach and to communicative action.

By coupling Habermas' scheme with previous tripartitions concerning regulation and participation, three different frameworks for relationships between research and society (the third mission of Universities) can be identified. Such different frameworks imply different kinds of stakeholders' participation each one connected to prevailing market, state or community logics. Figure 1 schematizes the resulting repartition that relates to Regulatory principles, Participation, Actors' Interests and potential Emancipation Dynamics (RePAIED). Such practices as patenting, spin off creation and paying activities for third parties all fall within the knowledge transfer dimension. On the other hand, science dissemination, evidence based policies, public hearings, citizen science, science museums, science festivals and continuing education are activities that can be resumed under the public engagement umbrella. That dimension partially overlaps with the community engagement one, which comprises such activities and experiences as community based and action research, service learning and science shops, deliberative science, bottom up approaches to citizens participation in science and technology assessment. Clearly enough, the scheme is not to be intended as a rigid structure and ambits cannot be so clear-cut (thus dimensions are marked with a dashed line). Rather, it is intended as an evolving and flexible conceptual map that can be used to identify specific dimensions of third mission and therefore be of guidance in the understanding of science-society relationships.

FIG. 1 – *Semantics of third mission: the RePAIED scheme*

V - FINAL NOTES TOWARDS FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

Such RePAIED scheme could eventually be useful also beyond the purpose of better defining specific dimensions of the semantics of third mission. Indeed, the theoretical discussion upon which it rests could also be applied to the research and teaching missions of universities, one may say. Which appears to be consistent with von Humboldt's classic conception of higher education as integrated by Mason's stool metaphor:

Higher education is a stool, and the stool has three legs: research, teaching, and service. There is a reason it has three legs. The service is there because it keeps the teaching and research honest. It keeps them connected to everyday problems that people have to address. And that is part of what the role of an institution of higher education ought to be (Mason, cited in Schuetze 2010: 17).

Building on such premises, the heuristic avail of the RePAIED scheme can be reconsidered in the frame of RRI and to the means of educating new generations of responsible researchers and innovators. For instance, one may question whether a teaching mission preeminently based upon market driven regulatory principles could be considerable as best fit to such a purpose. It may in fact be argued that students that

are taught in a market driven pedagogical environment would eventually be formed mainly to act *responsively* to market demands, rather than *responsibly* to society's or community's needs and expectations. In fact, be it connected with research or teaching mission, the underlying prevailing regulatory principles of the market, the state or the community establish definitely different relational sceneries which are characterized by different sets of interests (Habermas 1968; De Meulemeester 2011) and contingent expectations/anticipations (Parsons - Shils 1951) upon both research and teaching outputs and outcomes. That is to say that the prevalence of market, state or community regulatory principles as main drivers in the definition of a university's teaching, research and third mission would eventually shape very differentiated conceptions and models of responsibility.

As said, the knowledge transfer model is expected to originate responsive conducts and not necessarily responsible ones, although the latter cannot be excluded in principle of course. Rather, under certain conditions, such a model could be regarded as inherently irresponsible whereas its impacts on society at large are expected to undergo the depersonalized rules of the market that are mainly based on self interest and which do not necessarily produce positive collective externalities.

Indeed, more systematic confrontation of the tripartition synthesized in the RePAIED scheme against the fundamental requirements of RRI outlined above would eventually result in an interesting exercise to ascertain the implications of the different approaches. Regrettably, such an undertaking falls beyond the possibilities of this paper, as further theoretical discussion as well as empirical assessment would be needed. Nonetheless, some tentative thoughts can be here synthetically sketched that eventually prefigure further discussion and inquiry.

One first remark concerns the fact that community engagement appears to be better placed than public engagement and knowledge transfer approaches to fit in the European Commission's definition recalled above, which refers to RRI as an approach ensuring all relevant stakeholders' involvement in the research and innovation process in order to identify potential fallouts related to possible options and assess them in terms of societal needs and moral values, so to shape the development and designing of new research (EC 2013: 3).

Further considerations in that same direction can be advanced as to RRI process requirements identified by Kupper et al. (2015). Although, once again, more systematic and thorough assessment and crosscheck of possible interbreeds between the RePAIED scheme components and the four RRI process requirements would be needed, some issues can be here already pointed out. For instance, as to the openness and transparency requirement, which Kupper et al. identify as «conditions for accountability, liability and thus responsibility», one may remark that significant differences exist among the three dimensions of the RePAIED scheme. As a general rule, market based approaches tend to produce proprietary knowledge: restricted access to knowledge base is one main competitive factor for brand, firm or national economy positioning in the market and can be thus translated into market power. Typically, accountability and evaluation of impacts are in that case based upon such indicators as the number of patents, i.e. the quantity of proprietary knowledge that is produced by the research process. On

the other hand, the public engagement and community engagement approaches are both ideally incline to pursue social rather than just economic utility, and are therefore characterized by a tension towards openness of the research process and outputs. Nonetheless, in practice, conditions for transparency and forms for accountability may significantly differ between the two approaches. In fact, accountability measures which have been widely introduced in higher education systems by national governments in several parts of the world tend to privilege a «vertical» approach intended to make single institutions accountable to the central governing bodies: it is the logic of the supervising state which combines with – rather than replace – previous forms of controlling state based on more neweberian bureaucratic logics (van Vught 1994; Romzek 2000). On the other hand, a community engagement ideal type seems best suitable for social accountability measures (Vargiu 2014), although such an approach could not be in principle excluded from public engagement as well.

As said, such hypothesis should undergo further discussion and empirical testing in order for the RePAIED grid's appropriateness be confronted against all RRI process requirements. Yet, the above tentative example clearly shows the ideal typical nature of the proposed tripartition. Market, state or community driven models of university can be associated to material historical experiences: that is the case of the emerging model of entrepreneurial university (Clark 1998), for instance, as coherent with the market driven ideal type. Nonetheless, as a general rule, pluralism of organizational forms and blended approaches within single institutions are more likely to be empirically found than experiences clearly attributable to a single ideal typical model. Not only pluralism and blend of approaches and forms are widespread, but are also desirable, some state (Lessard 2012). Yet, such an intermixture is not to be intended as confusion of the three market, state and community dimensions. From an institution's governance point of view those three dimensions are to be conceived as differentiated although as possibly complementary strategic tensions. Certainly, provided that the national normative system adequately acknowledges those three dimensions and builds upon a clear yet not ideological perspective about them. And also provided that that same normative system allows enough room for universities to keep a hold on to adequate margins of substantial autonomy. As substantial autonomy is a precondition for real responsibility.

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